

AOV	4.0	15.00	14.29	13.40	14.23	5.533E+4	3.202E+2	3.828E+3	8.969E+3	1.365E+4	1.536E+4	8.445E+1	1.006E+3	4.100E+1	1.002E+2	1.472E+2	3.518E+2	6.704E+2	1.267E+3	1.733E+3	1.978E+3	1.645E+4	1.882E+2	7.767E+3	1.724E+4	1.748E+4	9.047E+3	7.157E+3
A3V	4.0	15.00	14.28	13.36	14.21	5.608E+4	2.731E+2	6.330E+3	8.984E+3	1.378E+4	1.589E+4	8.357E+1	9.799E+2	3.992E+1	8.418E+1	1.156E+2	3.191E+2	6.623E+2	1.247E+3	1.766E+3	1.991E+3	1.699E+4	1.745E+2	7.539E+3	1.739E+4	1.805E+4	9.380E+3	7.409E+3
ASV	4.0	15.00	14.21	13.25	14.12	5.977E+4	2.435E+2	3.387E+3	8.971E+3	1.463E+4	1.759E+4	7.999E+1	9.425E+2	3.484E+1	7.495E+1	1.026E+2	2.888E+2	6.377E+2	1.233E+3	1.736E+3	2.137E+3	1.884E+4	1.539E+2	7.249E+3	1.828E+4	1.984E+4	1.053E+4	8.300E+3
F2V	4.0	15.00	14.11	13.05	13.97	6.707E+4	2.181E+2	2.946E+3	8.968E+3	1.609E+4	2.110E+4	8.520E+1	8.789E+2	3.377E+1	6.693E+1	8.395E+1	2.278E+2	5.462E+2	1.145E+3	1.732E+3	2.440E+3	2.260E+4	1.468E+2	6.617E+3	1.977E+4	2.359E+4	1.299E+4	1.012E+4
F6V	4.0	15.00	14.04	12.91	13.87	7.281E+4	2.040E+2	2.743E+3	8.940E+3	1.716E+4	2.417E+4	8.939E+1	8.549E+2	3.307E+1	6.795E+1	7.715E+1	2.002E+2	5.115E+2	1.104E+3	1.729E+3	2.567E+3	2.530E+4	1.427E+2	6.340E+3	2.092E+4	2.666E+4	1.495E+4	1.134E+4
F8V	4.0	15.00	13.99	12.82	13.78	7.748E+4	1.855E+2	2.531E+3	8.921E+3	1.798E+4	2.595E+4	8.533E+1	8.050E+2	3.115E+1	5.643E+1	6.482E+1	1.798E+2	4.771E+2	1.082E+3	1.703E+3	2.758E+3	2.799E+4	1.341E+2	6.065E+3	2.169E+4	2.854E+4	1.667E+4	1.289E+4
G2V	4.0	15.00	13.95	12.72	13.72	8.178E+4	1.529E+2	2.367E+3	8.914E+3	1.860E+4	2.831E+4	8.179E+1	7.977E+2	2.581E+1	4.666E+1	5.257E+1	1.587E+2	4.518E+2	1.057E+3	1.693E+3	2.912E+3	3.055E+4	1.121E+2	5.835E+3	2.233E+4	3.089E+4	1.809E+4	1.420E+4
G3V	4.0	15.00	13.81	12.49	13.51	9.665E+4	1.208E+1	1.876E+3	8.910E+3	2.119E+4	3.495E+4	7.987E+1	6.991E+2	1.079E+1	1.911E+1	1.949E+1	9.392E+1	3.808E+2	8.816E+2	1.682E+3	3.356E+3	3.784E+4	4.849E+1	5.028E+3	2.503E+4	3.775E+4	2.362E+4	1.828E+4
K0V	4.0	15.00	13.48	11.81	12.91	1.588E+5	2.517E+1	1.273E+3	8.797E+3	2.785E+4	4.674E+4	6.015E+1	4.971E+2	1.435E+1	7.475E+1	8.770E+1	4.507E+1	2.995E+2	6.346E+2	1.612E+3	4.689E+3	7.066E+4	1.768E+1	3.861E+3	3.119E+4	6.739E+4	4.815E+4	3.684E+4
M8V	4.0	15.00	12.94	10.24	11.37	1.586E+5	1.554E+1	9.127E+2	8.348E+3	3.796E+4	2.603E+5	4.653E+1	4.051E+2	2.504E+1	5.242E+1	6.065E+1	2.359E+1	2.135E+2	7.248E+2	1.639E+3	7.704E+3	2.960E+5	1.091E+1	3.810E+3	3.864E+4	2.390E+5	2.756E+5	2.007E+5
G8III	4.0	15.00	13.63	12.50	13.52	9.564E+4	5.987E+1	1.846E+3	8.890E+3	2.071E+4	3.465E+4	7.697E+1	6.939E+2	9.527E+1	1.877E+1	2.004E+1	8.926E+1	3.721E+2	9.475E+2	1.667E+3	3.229E+3	3.705E+4	4.522E+1	5.082E+3	2.451E+4	3.723E+4	2.365E+4	1.806E+4
K3III	4.0	15.00	13.68	12.30	13.32	7.281E+4	1.496E+3	8.875E+3	2.392E+4	4.117E+4	7.051E+4	6.133E+2	4.482E+1	9.231E+1	1.012E+1	1.132E+1	2.002E+1	3.139E+2	8.054E+2	1.642E+3	3.793E+3	4.503E+4	2.001E+4	4.435E+3	2.773E+4	4.431E+4	3.012E+4	2.300E+4
M0III	4.0	15.00	13.51	11.79	12.87	1.627E+5	1.204E+1	1.144E+3	8.784E+3	2.727E+4	6.514E+4	5.553E+1	4.958E+2	1.713E+1	3.847E+1	4.072E+1	2.948E+1	2.604E+2	7.023E+2	1.623E+3	4.434E+3	7.215E+4	8.278E+0	3.887E+3	3.098E+4	6.643E+4	5.305E+4	3.975E+4
M7III	4.0	15.00	12.14	8.00	9.66	2.602E+6	3.465E+1	7.097E+2	7.602E+3	5.623E+4	8.904E+5	2.198E+1	2.499E+2	2.329E+1	1.198E+1	1.654E+1	8.009E+1	8.957E+1	6.721E+2	1.472E+3	1.128E+4	1.106E+6	1.748E+1	3.096E+3	6.446E+4	7.836E+4	1.616E+6	1.071E+6
B0IB	4.0	15.00	14.42	13.70	14.43	4.876E+4	9.026E+2	4.487E+3	8.964E+3	1.216E+4	1.176E+4	1.300E+2	1.144E+3	1.911E+2	2.582E+2	2.741E+2	4.327E+2	7.343E+2	1.322E+3	1.765E+3	1.859E+3	1.251E+4	7.476E+2	8.523E+3	1.581E+4	1.353E+4	6.450E+3	5.220E+3
B1V	5.0	15.00	14.24	13.32	14.17	5.802E+4	5.189E+2	3.568E+3	8.942E+3	1.434E+4	1.667E+4	1.093E+2	9.780E+2	1.014E+2	1.515E+2	1.696E+2	3.198E+2	6.146E+2	1.257E+3	1.733E+3	2.256E+3	1.776E+4	4.053E+2	7.450E+3	1.800E+4	1.890E+4	9.483E+3	7.499E+3
A3V	5.0	15.00	14.10	12.98	13.91	6.985E+4	1.675E+2	2.773E+3	8.983E+3	1.616E+4	2.237E+4	6.942E+1	8.155E+2	2.286E+1	5.217E+1	7.330E+1	2.182E+2	5.232E+2	1.134E+3	1.748E+3	2.362E+3	2.415E+4	1.023E+2	6.423E+3	1.980E+4	2.474E+4	1.473E+4	1.147E+4
ASV	5.0	15.00	14.04	12.87	13.87	8.506E+4	1.492E+2	2.589E+3	8.965E+3	1.718E+4	2.473E+4	6.636E+1	7.834E+2	1.992E+1	4.640E+1	6.492E+1	1.972E+2	5.029E+2	1.121E+3	1.716E+3	2.532E+3	2.675E+4	9.010E+1	1.817E+3	2.084E+4	2.716E+4	1.650E+4	1.283E+4
F2V	5.0	15.00	13.94	12.67	13.65	8.547E+4	1.327E+2	2.251E+3	8.950E+3	1.883E+4	2.957E+4	7.045E+1	7.276E+2	1.925E+1	4.117E+1	5.285E+1	1.548E+2	4.292E+2	1.036E+3	1.698E+3	2.878E+3	3.199E+4	8.573E+1	6.595E+3	2.249E+4	3.221E+4	2.030E+4	1.559E+4
F6V	5.0	15.00	13.87	12.53	13.55	9.350E+4	1.242E+2	2.097E+3	8.904E+3	2.010E+4	3.383E+4	7.373E+1	7.061E+2	1.882E+1	3.838E+1	4.629E+1	1.373E+2	4.012E+2	9.980E+2	1.693E+3	3.023E+3	3.657E+4	8.317E+1	5.433E+3	2.383E+4	3.636E+4	2.269E+4	1.743E+4
F8V	5.0	15.00	13.82	12.44	13.46	1.002E+5	1.121E+2	1.934E+3	8.888E+3	2.103E+4	3.627E+4	7.023E+1	6.641E+2	1.769E+1	3.451E+1	4.062E+1	1.218E+2	3.735E+2	9.762E+2	1.671E+3	3.242E+3	3.952E+4	7.795E+1	5.206E+3	2.467E+4	3.886E+4	2.595E+4	1.977E+4
G2V	5.0	15.00	13.78	12.35	13.39	1.063E+5	9.221E+1	1.813E+3	8.878E+3	2.176E+4	3.952E+4	7.330E+1	6.573E+2	1.464E+1	2.848E+1	3.290E+1	1.074E+2	3.533E+2	9.521E+2	1.663E+3	3.419E+3	4.309E+4	6.513E+1	5.028E+3	2.539E+4	4.204E+4	2.806E+4	2.176E+4
G3V	5.0	15.00	13.64	12.12	13.17	1.269E+5	3.707E+1	1.439E+3	8.857E+3	2.465E+4	4.850E+4	6.439E+1	6.087E+2	1.154E+1	1.212E+1	6.311E+1	2.958E+1	7.902E+2	1.638E+3	3.914E+3	5.306E+4	2.803E+1	4.340E+3	5.107E+4	3.649E+4	2.782E+4	2.080E+4	1.782E+4
M0V	5.0	15.00	13.31	11.45	12.56	2.132E+5	1.490E+1	7.919E+2	8.875E+3	3.191E+4	8.887E+4	8.850E+1	4.022E+2	2.302E+1	4.640E+1	5.306E+1	3.036E+1	2.296E+2	5.617E+2	1.551E+3	4.401E+3	9.804E+4	1.011E+1	3.335E+3	3.506E+4	9.032E+4	7.352E+4	5.541E+4
M8V	5.0	15.00	12.73	9.87	10.96	3.371E+5	9.219E+0	7.038E+2	8.218E+3	4.448E+4	3.602E+5	3.757E+1	3.287E+2	1.393E+1	3.148E+1	3.733E+1	1.568E+1	1.649E+2	4.421E+2	1.574E+3	8.878E+3	4.148E+5	6.218E+0	3.360E+3	4.404E+4	3.246E+5	4.231E+5	3.072E+5
G8III	5.0	15.00	13.66	12.12	13.18	1.285E+5	3.590E+1	1.418E+3	8.839E+3	2.412E+4	4.814E+4	6.269E+1	5.689E+2	5.382E+1	1.135E+1	1.248E+1	6.004E+1	2.884E+2	8.490E+2	1.625E+3	3.771E+3	5.287E+4	6.232E+1	4.396E+3	2.777E+4	5.045E+4	3.661E+4	2.525E+4
K3III	5.0	15.00	13.51	11.93	12.98	1.489E+5	1.741E+1	1.149E+3	8.806E+3	2.778E+4	5.687E+4	5.729E+1	4.980E+2	2.520E+1	5.553E+1	6.266E+1	3.521E+1	2.402E+2	7.174E+2	1.591E+3	4.401E+3	6.290E+4	1.208E+1	3.845E+3	3.134E+4	5.966E+4	4.635E+4	3.483E+4
M0III	5.0	15.00	13.33	11.42	12.51	2.203E+5	7.164E+0	8.805E+2	8.696E+3	3.162E+4	8.974E+4	4.490E+1	4.024E+2	9.598E-1	2.307E+1	6.265E+1	1.964E+1	2.003E+2	6.228E+2	1.565E+3	5.120E+3	1.006E+5	4.763E+0	3.389E+3	4.999E+4	8.136E+4	5.996E+4	
M7III	5.0	15.00	11.92	8.44	9.23	3.826E+6	2.060E+1	5.248E+2	7.393E+3	7.617E+4	1.218E+6	1.750E+1	2.004E+2	1.296E+1	7.108E+1	1.003E+1	5.294E+1	7.487E+1	5.843E+2	1.395E+3	1.281E+4	1.540E+6	1.011E+3	2.684E+3	3.374E+4	1.057E+6	2.502E+6	1.597E+6
B0IB	5.0	15.00	14.24	13.31	14.16	5.824E+4	5.488E+2	3.422E+3	8.977E+3	1.427E+4	1.663E+4	1.084E+2	9.556E+2	1.097E+2	1.597E+2	1.740E+2	2.969E+2	5.825E+2	1.207E+3	1.754E+3	2.214E+3	1.784E+4	4.359E+2	7.219E+3	1.802E+4	1.815E+4	1.015E+4	8.19E+3

Table 2: CCD#3 (Astro)

Pupil area (m²) = 1.190000

Quantum efficiency (CCD#3) and telescope transmittance (excluding filters):

Lambda	300	325	350	375	400	425	450	475	500	525	550	575	600	625	650	675	700	725	750	775	800	825	850	875	900	925	950	975	1000	1025	1050	1075	1100	
QE	.000	.025	.050	.130	.210	.405	.600	.685	.770	.795	.820	.860	.900	.905	.910	.910	.910	.875	.840	.805	.770	.715	.660	.605	.550	.465	.380	.290	.200	.100	.000	.000	.000	
Topt	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900	.900

Filter characteristics:

	lambda0	700.00	U	B	V	Rc	Ic	Bn	Bw	35	37	38	41	47	52	55	66	81	u'	g'	r'	i'	z'	z''
	FWHM	800.00	50.00	100.00	100.00	150.00	140.00	3.00	25.00	30.00	26.00	20.00	19.00	18.00	21.00	23.00	20.00	166.00	60.00	150.00	150.00	250.00	100.00	
	Tmax	1.00	.85	.88	.95	.72	.96	3.70	.70	.														

F2V	2.0	15.00	14.46	13.83	14.51	5.532E+4	1.152E+2	3.366E+3	8.780E+3	1.303E+4	1.532E+4	1.043E+2	1.072E+3	1.263E+1	3.775E+1	5.128E+1	1.941E+2	6.733E+2	1.271E+3	1.683E+3	1.946E+3	1.656E+4	6.612E+4	7.326E+3	1.658E+4	1.699E+4	1.105E+4	8.036E+3
F2V	2.0	15.00	14.39	13.68	14.43	5.984E+4	1.077E+2	3.155E+3	8.762E+3	1.391E+4	1.762E+4	1.097E+2	1.046E+3	1.242E+1	3.523E+1	4.506E+1	1.732E+2	6.326E+2	1.229E+3	1.686E+3	2.054E+3	1.902E+4	6.439E+4	7.044E+3	1.755E+4	1.926E+4	1.241E+4	9.027E+3
F2V	2.0	15.00	14.34	13.59	14.36	6.376E+4	9.715E+1	2.932E+3	8.774E+3	1.461E+4	1.899E+4	1.051E+2	9.891E+2	1.172E+1	3.177E+1	3.976E+1	1.547E+2	5.923E+2	1.210E+3	1.674E+3	2.215E+3	2.067E+4	6.054E+4	6.761E+3	1.824E+4	2.070E+4	1.432E+4	1.030E+4
GBV	2.0	15.00	14.30	13.49	14.31	6.711E+4	8.007E+1	2.761E+3	8.779E+3	1.514E+4	2.077E+4	1.101E+2	9.826E+2	9.749E+0	2.626E+1	3.232E+1	1.369E+2	5.622E+2	1.184E+3	1.671E+3	2.344E+3	2.262E+4	5.089E+4	6.522E+3	1.880E+4	2.247E+4	1.547E+4	1.138E+4
K3V	2.0	15.00	14.15	13.24	14.12	7.988E+4	3.259E+1	2.250E+3	8.840E+3	1.744E+4	2.604E+4	1.000E+2	8.735E+2	4.154E+0	1.074E+1	1.216E+1	6.202E+1	4.807E+2	1.001E+3	1.680E+3	2.741E+3	2.845E+4	2.247E+4	5.697E+3	2.131E+4	2.787E+4	2.063E+4	1.486E+4
M0V	2.0	15.00	13.82	12.54	13.57	1.329E+5	1.375E+1	1.589E+3	8.863E+3	2.336E+4	4.959E+4	7.732E+1	6.372E+2	1.626E+0	4.543E+0	5.622E+0	4.125E+1	3.880E+2	7.378E+2	1.652E+3	3.930E+3	5.464E+4	8.409E+0	4.467E+3	2.707E+4	5.115E+4	4.334E+4	3.077E+4
M0V	2.0	15.00	13.35	10.99	12.17	1.494E+5	5.166E+0	1.142E+3	8.441E+3	3.116E+4	2.000E+5	5.065E+5	5.975E+2	1.639E+2	9.782E-1	3.079E-0	3.882E+0	2.105E+1	2.755E+2	4.399E+2	1.679E+3	6.435E+3	2.299E+5	5.130E+0	4.338E+3	2.864E+4	1.819E+5	2.072E+5
G8III	2.0	15.00	14.18	13.25	14.14	7.896E+4	3.172E+1	2.207E+3	8.810E+3	1.701E+4	2.572E+4	9.572E+1	8.641E+2	3.666E+0	1.054E+1	1.247E+1	7.749E+1	4.682E+2	1.073E+3	1.660E+3	2.629E+3	2.821E+4	2.115E+4	5.740E+3	2.081E+4	2.739E+4	2.069E+4	1.463E+4
K3III	2.0	15.00	14.02	13.04	13.95	9.358E+4	1.577E+1	1.832E+3	8.859E+3	1.982E+4	3.099E+4	8.919E+1	7.132E+2	1.765E+0	5.265E+0	6.389E+0	4.639E+1	4.002E+2	9.234E+2	1.656E+3	3.128E+3	4.232E+4	9.979E+0	5.070E+3	2.375E+4	3.305E+4	2.671E+4	1.889E+4
M0III	2.0	15.00	13.85	12.53	13.55	1.361E+5	6.266E+0	1.428E+3	8.826E+3	2.272E+4	4.962E+4	7.995E+1	6.318E+2	6.810E-1	2.229E+0	2.729E+0	2.645E+1	3.353E+2	8.129E+2	1.654E+3	3.694E+3	5.553E+4	4.005E+0	4.465E+3	2.666E+4	5.012E+4	4.780E+4	3.299E+4
M7III	2.0	15.00	12.57	9.54	10.51	2.377E+6	2.106E+1	8.571E+2	7.879E+3	5.421E+4	7.061E+5	2.892E+1	3.274E+2	1.007E+0	7.135E+0	1.087E+0	7.386E+1	1.307E+2	8.058E+2	1.540E+3	9.686E+3	8.902E+5	9.571E+0	5.508E+3	5.503E+4	6.165E+5	1.583E+6	9.288E+5
B0IB	2.0	15.00	14.76	14.49	14.84	4.855E+4	4.450E+2	4.918E+3	8.680E+3	9.759E+3	8.370E+3	1.559E+2	1.370E+3	6.941E+1	1.485E+2	1.635E+2	3.605E+2	2.877E+2	1.439E+3	1.691E+3	1.454E+3	8.973E+3	3.158E+2	9.243E+3	1.313E+4	9.552E+3	5.320E+3	4.860E+3
B1V	3.0	15.00	14.59	14.10	14.67	4.783E+4	2.615E+2	3.986E+3	8.707E+3	1.153E+4	1.197E+4	1.323E+2	1.181E+3	3.721E+1	8.365E+1	1.021E+2	2.697E+2	7.498E+2	1.381E+3	1.675E+3	1.781E+3	1.286E+4	1.749E+2	8.154E+3	1.498E+4	1.346E+4	7.940E+3	5.888E+3
A0V	3.0	15.00	14.46	13.79	14.49	5.655E+4	1.081E+2	3.317E+3	8.782E+3	1.296E+4	1.569E+4	8.592E+1	1.022E+3	8.756E+0	3.574E+1	5.733E+1	2.052E+2	6.529E+2	1.279E+3	1.675E+3	1.872E+3	1.714E+4	5.067E+1	7.291E+3	1.647E+4	1.724E+4	1.210E+4	8.800E+3
A3V	3.0	15.00	14.45	13.76	14.47	5.757E+4	9.025E+1	3.169E+3	8.801E+3	1.309E+4	1.627E+4	8.498E+1	9.960E+2	8.560E+0	2.973E+1	4.501E+1	1.863E+2	6.455E+2	1.260E+3	1.708E+3	1.886E+3	1.773E+4	4.649E+1	7.105E+3	1.662E+4	1.784E+4	1.255E+4	9.119E+3
A5V	3.0	15.00	14.39	13.64	14.40	6.173E+4	8.082E+1	2.977E+3	8.799E+3	1.392E+4	1.803E+4	8.145E+1	9.593E+2	7.463E+0	2.654E+1	3.996E+1	1.692E+2	6.223E+2	1.248E+3	1.681E+3	2.027E+3	1.969E+4	4.106E+1	6.866E+3	1.749E+4	1.963E+4	1.412E+4	1.022E+4
F2V	3.0	15.00	14.28	13.44	14.26	7.038E+4	7.150E+1	2.622E+3	8.826E+3	1.536E+4	2.177E+4	8.721E+1	8.980E+2	7.316E+0	2.355E+1	3.270E+1	1.338E+2	5.355E+2	1.163E+3	1.677E+3	3.232E+3	2.377E+4	3.947E+1	6.327E+3	1.899E+4	2.350E+4	1.755E+4	1.254E+4
F6V	3.0	15.00	14.22	13.24	14.16	7.684E+4	6.665E+1	2.460E+3	8.801E+3	1.641E+4	2.500E+4	9.157E+1	8.750E+2	7.186E+0	2.192E+1	2.867E+1	1.192E+2	5.023E+2	1.124E+3	1.677E+3	2.449E+3	2.727E+4	8.37E+0	6.093E+3	2.012E+4	2.664E+4	1.969E+4	1.405E+4
F8V	3.0	15.00	14.17	13.20	14.09	8.258E+4	5.992E+1	2.284E+3	8.807E+3	1.722E+4	2.692E+4	8.756E+1	8.260E+2	6.763E+0	1.971E+1	2.525E+1	1.063E+2	4.694E+2	1.104E+3	1.662E+3	2.636E+3	2.961E+4	3.598E+1	5.856E+3	2.090E+4	2.858E+4	2.268E+4	1.600E+4
GBV	3.0	15.00	14.13	13.11	14.02	8.740E+4	4.929E+1	2.155E+3	8.809E+3	1.783E+4	2.914E+4	9.162E+1	8.195E+2	5.621E+0	1.626E+1	2.049E+1	9.394E+1	4.450E+2	1.079E+3	1.658E+3	2.786E+3	3.237E+4	3.023E+1	5.661E+3	2.153E+4	3.300E+4	2.445E+4	1.766E+4
K3V	3.0	15.00	13.98	12.86	13.82	1.055E+5	1.986E+1	1.756E+3	8.854E+3	2.044E+4	3.663E+4	8.264E+1	7.232E+2	2.380E+0	6.571E+0	7.655E+0	5.586E+1	3.778E+2	9.061E+2	1.655E+3	3.234E+3	4.047E+4	1.327E+1	4.954E+3	2.430E+4	3.822E+4	3.241E+4	2.290E+4
M0V	3.0	15.00	13.65	12.17	13.25	1.805E+5	8.300E+0	1.231E+3	8.838E+3	2.717E+4	6.897E+4	6.305E+1	5.214E+2	9.189E-1	2.756E+0	3.495E+0	2.776E+1	3.009E+2	6.602E+2	1.607E+3	4.577E+3	7.685E+4	4.907E+0	3.881E+3	3.064E+4	6.944E+4	6.729E+4	4.685E+4
M8V	3.0	15.00	13.14	10.61	11.77	7.202E+5	5.159E+0	8.941E+2	8.379E+3	3.681E+4	2.806E+5	4.869E+1	4.246E+2	5.534E-1	1.876E+0	2.421E+0	1.418E+1	2.143E+2	7.529E+2	1.632E+3	7.507E+3	3.269E+5	2.990E+0	3.852E+3	3.776E+4	2.505E+5	3.919E+5	2.550E+5
G8III	3.0	15.00	14.00	12.87	13.84	1.045E+5	1.941E+1	1.725E+3	8.826E+3	1.996E+4	3.623E+4	7.922E+1	7.171E+2	2.105E+0	6.463E+0	7.865E+0	5.284E+1	3.686E+2	9.725E+2	1.630E+3	3.107E+3	4.019E+4	1.254E+1	5.004E+3	2.376E+4	3.762E+4	3.258E+4	2.258E+4
K3III	3.0	15.00	13.85	12.67	13.65	1.249E+5	9.598E+0	1.430E+3	8.858E+3	2.318E+4	4.340E+4	7.333E+1	6.358E+2	4.008E+0	3.211E+0	4.006E+0	3.143E+1	3.130E+2	8.319E+2	1.622E+3	3.673E+3	4.849E+4	5.886E+0	4.424E+3	2.703E+4	4.580E+4	4.181E+4	2.897E+4
M0III	3.0	15.00	13.68	12.16	13.22	1.867E+5	4.018E+0	1.115E+3	8.805E+3	2.652E+4	6.928E+4	5.804E+1	5.186E+2	3.874E-1	1.355E+0	1.703E+0	1.785E+1	2.610E+2	7.289E+2	1.613E+3	4.115E+3	7.849E+4	2.352E+0	3.915E+3	3.032E+4	6.833E+4	7.455E+4	5.037E+4
M7III	3.0	15.00	12.35	9.17	10.08	3.549E+6	1.274E+1	6.487E+2	7.736E+3	6.396E+4	9.809E+5	2.333E+1	2.662E+2	5.700E-1	4.407E+0	6.686E+0	4.966E+1	1.006E+2	2.097E+2	1.486E+3	1.155E+4	1.259E+6	5.641E+0	3.121E+3	6.358E+4	8.440E+5	2.460E+6	1.392E+6
B0IB	3.0	15.00	14.59	14.09	14.66	4.813E+4	2.765E+2	3.832E+3	8.751E+3	1.153E+4	1.200E+4	1.316E+2	1.158E+3	4.050E+1	8.815E+1	1.051E+2	2.507E+2	7.128E+2	1.330E+3	1.700E+3	1.753E+3	1.299E+4	1.883E+2	7.920E+3	1.506E+4	1.332E+4	8.509E+3	6.388E+3
B1V	4.0	15.00	14.41	13.71	14.44	5.922E+4	1.622E+2	3.105E+3	8.763E+3	1.363E+4	1.708E+4	1.112E+2	9.946E+2	2.162E+1	5.232E+1	6.540E+1	1.868E+2	5.993E+2	1.271E+3	1.677E+3	2.138E+3	1.853E+4	1.042E+2	7.025E+3	1.721E+4	1.869E+4	1.266E+4	9.227E+3
A0V	4.0	15.00	14.29	13.40	14.23	7.238E+4	6.759E+1	2.579E+3	8.827E+3	1.529E+4	2.231E+4	7.186E+1	8.570E+2	5.069E+0	2.240E+1	3.664E+1	1.415E+2	5.193E+2	1.172E+3	1.609E+3	2.250E+3	2.464E+4	3.036E+1	6.298E+3	1.887E+4	2.386E+4	1.923E+4	1.373E+4
A3V	4.0	15.00	14.28	13.36	14.21	7.396E+4	5.621E+1	2.466E+3	8.844E+3	1.544E+4	2.313E+4	7.102E+1	8.341E+2	4.955E+0	1.858E+1	2.874E+1	1.284E+2	5.131E+2	1.153E+3	1.701E+3	2.250E+3	2.547E+4	2.778E+1	6.149E+3	1.903E+4	2.468E+4	1.995E+4	1.422E+4
A5V	4.0	15.00	14.21	13.25	14.17	7.996E+4	5.031E+1	2.318E+3	8.837E+3	1.642E+4	2.560E+4	6.798E+1	8.025E+2	4.313E+0	1.657E+1	2.547E+1	1.165E+2	4.939E+2	1.141E+3	1.672E+3	2.416E+3	2.826E+4	2.451E+1	5.951E+3	2.005E+4	2.713E+4	2.241E+4	1.592E+4
F2V	4.0	15.00	14.11	13.05	13.97	9.237E+4	4.418E+1	2.038E+3	8.854E+3	1.807E+4	3.081E+4	7.247E+1	7.487E+2	4.215E+0	1.461E+1	2.161E+1	9.167E+1	4.233E+2	1.059E+3	1.661E+3	2.758E+3	3.399E+4	2.347E+1	5.490E+3	2.172E+4	3.240E+4	2.776E+4	1.945E+4
F6V	4.0	15.00	14.04	12.91	13.87	1.015E+5	4.106E+1	1.914E+3	8.821E+3	1.931E+4	3.532E+4	7.599E+1	7.277E+2	4.134E+0	1.356E+1	1.813E+1	8.154E+1	3.964E+2	1.022E+3	1.659E+3	2.902E+3	3.895E+4	2.277E+1	5.295E+3	2.303E+4	3.609E+4	3.107E+4	2.175E+4
F8V	4.0	15.00	13.99	12.82	13.78	1.099E+5	3.678E+1	1.776E+3	8.821E+3	2.024E+4	3.799E+4	7.251																